

THE BENEFITS OF USING GAMIFICATION IN UZBEK LANGUAGE LESSONS

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Abstract: This article considers the main advantages of using various applications for learning Uzbek language in a playful way. The game in the best way allows students to achieve metasubjective results of learning a language, such as the ability to memorize new material without much effort, the ability to choose speech means for successfully solving a communicative task. The article involves the teacher in the search for the most interesting, informative, effective teaching platforms.

Keywords: gamification, applications, advantages, platforms, learning, educational application, mobile applications.

Introduction

Today's learners are very close to technology. They even are labeled as digital natives because they get along very well and cannot be separated from it. The product of technology that is most frequently used by students is games. One study conducted mentioned that students at the age of teenagers spent averagely eight to ten hours in a day playing games, either online or offline. It can be learned from the study that there is a close relationship between students and the games that they spent most of their days playing them. This would bring great effects on the aspects of their lives, not to exclude their school lives. If teachers are not aware of this, there will be a wide gap that can cause conflicts between teachers and students in learning.

One of the ways to bridge this phenomenon is that the teachers have to embrace games in the learning process, and implementing gamification is the most promising one.

Through the use of game-based elements, teaching and learning turn into a more collaborative and enjoyable process. The purpose of implementing the gamification concept in education is to maximize learner's motivation and engagement. The main focus of gamification should be on the learner to make a desirable change in behavior. Gatautis et al¹. claim that gamification is mainly employed to direct users' behavior. However, on the other hand, Calderón et al². argue that implementing gamification is not only about encouraging users through the use of game elements. It is instead an application lesson using in the nongame position, such as training and education. Also, Yildirim shows that gamification positively impacts achievement and behaviors against learning objectives³.

Main part

At the present time, due to the development of globalization and the significant progress of high technologies, the importance of learning language is increasing even from an early age.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev, in his annual missive to the people of Uzbekistan, considered the state program “Digital Uzbekistan”. The Head of State noted that it is essential to continue work on the development of digital

¹ Gatautis, R., Vitkauskaitė, E., Gadeikiene, A., & Piligrimiene, Z. (2016). Gamification as a mean of driving online consumer behavior: model perspective. *Engineering Economics*, 27(1), 90-97. <https://doi.org/10.5755/j01.ee.27.1.13198>

² Calderón, A., Boubeta-Puig, J., & Ruiz, M. (2018). MEdit4CEP-Gam: A model-driven approach for user-friendly gamification design, monitoring and code generation in CEP-based systems. *Information and Software Technology*, 95, 238-264. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infsof.2017.11.009>

³ Yildirim, I. (2017). The effects of gamification-based teaching practices on student achievement and students' attitudes toward lessons. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 33, 86-92. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2017.02.002>

educational resources, connecting to the broadband Internet and equipping our schools with video equipment.

“Moreover, it is absolutely important to improve the skills of people. We must learn how to use smartphones, as it should. Therefore, here we have a huge field of work, and we need to explicate and learn more”, - the Head of States believes.- “All Uzbekistanis, from schoolchildren to pensioners, need to sit back at the books and learn new technologies”⁴.

In any kind of activity there is particular importance how students are motivated to perform actions in the classroom. As applied to teaching language in order to create sustained interest and motivate students to achieve results, allow gaming educational technologies or gamification.

Gamification is the application of game-design elements and game principles in nongame context⁵. Gamification commonly employs game design elements⁶ to improve user engagement, organizational productivity flow, learning, crowdsourcing, employee recruitment and evaluation, ease of use, usefulness of systems, physical exercise, traffic violations, voter apathy, and more⁷.

The main discrepancy between gamification and other educational technologies based on the principles of the game is the use of high-tech approaches, such as iPhones, laptops, smartphones, tablets, in education with the aim of increasing students' involvement in the learning process.

Consider the advantages of this approach:

⁴ President Shavkat Mirziyoyev chaired a meeting of video selectors on measures to improve the language teaching system. 6-may, 2021.

⁵ Huotari K. & Hamari J., 2012. “Defining Gamification- A Service Marketing Perspective” (PDF). Proceedings of the 16th International Academic MindTrek Conference, 2012. Tampere, Finland. October 3-5.

⁶ Robson K., Plangger K., Kietzmann J., McCarthy I. & Pitt L., 2015. “Is it all a game? Understanding the principles of gamification”. Business Horizons. 58 (4): 411-420.

⁷ Hamari J., Koivisto J., 2015. “Why do people use gamification services?” International Journal of Information Management. 35 (4): 419-431.

1. Gamification allows teachers to make the process of learning a foreign language bright, interesting, colorful;
2. The game is capable of almost every student, even one who does not have sufficiently strong knowledge of the language;
3. During the game, the material is remembered easier, without unnecessary volitional efforts;
4. During the game, additional positive emotions appear that not only improve the process of memorization, but also increase motivation;
5. A student who is weak in language can be the first in the game: resourcefulness and ingenuity here are more important than knowledge in the subject;
6. A sense of equality, an atmosphere of enthusiasm and joy, a sense of feasibility of the tasks- all this enables the student to overcome his shyness, which prevents student from using the words of foreign language in speech, reduces the fear of mistakes, and has a beneficial effect on learning outcomes;
7. Quietly assimilated linguistic material, and with it a feeling of satisfaction arises; the student can already speak on a par with everyone.

Thus, a lesson built with the use of gamification allows teachers to keep students' attention, leaves no one indifferent in the class, “infects” with a positive and emotionally adjusts to a useful mood. The basic principle of gamification is constant feedback with the learner. The teacher always has the opportunity to adjust the learning process, keeping the attention of the class. Elements of gamification are easily applicable for both group and individual activities suitable for all ages.

[Interacty](#) website is one of the best sites that includes gamification methods. With the help of this site, it becomes easier for us to learn the Uzbek language.

Interacty is a web-based development platform that allows to create engaging interactive content. We help publishers and brands create quizzes, photo stories, memory games and other interactive formats. Interacty provides free online storytelling tools, engaging your users and surprising them by unique formats. Add interactivity to your site or blog, promote your business and get more shares on facebook. A powerful online editor and instant publishing are available for free. Start from a minimal layout or customize a ready-made project. Just add your content, logotype and publish. All projects are available on mobile devices.

Figure 1. Interactive games section of the website Interacty

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Figure 2. View of the spin interactive game on the website

Discover endless possibilities with Spin the Wheel - Random Picker Wheel Maker! Unleash your creativity and design custom spin wheels for any occasion. Whether it's for games, giveaways, or decision-making fun, our user-friendly platform lets you create interactive experiences that engage and entertain. Spin the wheel and make your ideas come to life in a dynamic and exciting way!

Kahoot! It: Gamification in Higher Education

This paper focused on investigating Kahoot! as the gamified product to boost the learning environment among language learners in higher education in

Uzbekistan. The result indicated that the students found Kahoot! beneficial in inducing motivation and engagement, as well as fostering and reinforcing learning for both theoretical and practical aspects. The results reflected the respondents' attitudes towards Kahoot! was notably positive, with a percentage of 100%. They experienced that Kahoot! could bring effectiveness in their academic context. 98% of them found that Kahoot! interesting, fun, and enjoyable; meanwhile, 96% answered that Kahoot! brought the atmosphere of competitiveness that they were triggered to do each Kahoot! session.

Conclusion

This study has confirmed that gamification is indeed beneficial for students in the Uzbek language class. It appears to be the solution for an unsuccessful and passive learning environment as it is beneficial to assist teachers in creating a more exciting and meaningful learning experience for students. A livelier learning environment, more active engagement, better Uzbek skills, and improved cognitive achievements are the indicators of successful implementation of gamification in the Uzbek language class. Therefore, it is highly recommended for the language teachers who have problems with their class, especially in terms of activeness and Uzbek language skills, to apply gamification in their classes.

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